

DISTRIBUTION OF HAEMOGLOBIN GENOTYPES AND MALARIA PREVALENCE IN NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA.

By

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ABSTRACT

Malaria remains a significant health challenge in Nigeria, particularly in areas with high transmission rates. This study investigated the relationship between haemoglobin genotypes and malaria susceptibility **in the three Senatorial zones** of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. A hospital-based cross-sectional survey was carried out from January 13, 2025, to May 22, 2025 in Nasarawa State. Convenient sampling was used for selecting the study. A total of 384 malaria patients diagnosed by microscopy were included in the study, and their haemoglobin genotypes were determined using cellulose acetate electrophoresis. The results showed that AA genotype was the most prevalent (79.9%), followed by AS (19.3%), SS (0.5%), and AC (0.3%). Though the p-value was insignificant, the distribution of malaria parasitaemia was higher in individuals with the AA genotype, suggesting that this genotype is more susceptible to malaria. The AS and SS genotypes appeared to offer some protection against malaria, consistent with previous studies. These findings highlight the importance of haemoglobin variants in malaria susceptibility and

have implications for malaria prevention and treatment strategies. The findings of this study are particularly important especially in high-transmission regions, and therefore calls for expanded multi-states studies to further understand the complex relationships between haemoglobin genotypes and malaria susceptibility. This could inform targeted medicine and contribute to understanding malaria susceptibility in similar populations.

Keywords: Malaria Parasite, Haemoglobin Genotypes, Susceptibility, Prevalence, Nasarawa State.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest health challenges of mankind is malaria, especially in endemic populations such as sub-saharan Africa. Malaria develops when an individual receives a bite from an infected female Anopheles mosquito, leading to the injection of malaria parasites (MPs, also known as Plasmodium species) into the human body. Globally, it was estimated that 627,000 deaths occurred in 2021 (WHO, 2022), though this represents a small fraction of the over 200 million clinical cases per year. Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance, stated that new data from the World Health Organisation (WHO) revealed that an estimated 263 million malaria cases and 597,000 malaria deaths occurred worldwide in 2023 (WHO, 2024). This marks an increase of approximately 11 million cases compared to 2022, with nearly the same number of deaths reported (WHO, 2023). Alarmingly, about 95 per cent of these deaths were concentrated in the WHO African region, where many individuals at risk still lack access to essential services for prevention, detection, and treatment of malaria (WHO, 2024).

Human malaria is caused by one of five species of the single-celled eukaryotic genus *Plasmodium*; with the highest disease burden caused by *P. falciparum* (Phillips *et al.*, 2017; Cowman *et al.*, 2016). *Plasmodium* parasites have a complex lifestyle that entails sexual reproduction in the Anopheles vector and asexual reproduction in the human host (Cowman *et al.*, 2016; Aly *et al.*, 2009). Human infection begins when sporozoites are delivered into the skin by the bites of an infected Anopheles mosquito. Sporozoites travel from the skin via the bloodstream to the liver, where they invade hepatocytes. During the liver stages, a single parasite gives rise to tens of thousands of merozoites which are then released into the bloodstream initiating the symptomatic blood stage of a *Plasmodium* infection by replicating inside of erythrocytes. Importantly, while only tens to hundreds of sporozoites are injected into the dermis per mosquito bite, one successfully developing sporozoite is enough to cause blood stage infection with an average of 7×10^{11} blood-borne parasites (Dondorp *et al.*, 2005). A subset of these blood stages will develop into sexual stage gametocytes which can continue the cycle of infection if taken up during blood feeding by another mosquito (Aly *et al.*, 2009).

Symptoms of malaria range from none in partially immune individuals, to cyclic fever and to severe manifestations leading to death. However, only around 1% of clinical infections lead to severe malaria, most often in immunological naïve individuals (Phillips *et al.*, 2017). Accordingly, in endemic areas children under 5 years of age are most affected and most likely to suffer from severe malaria and death (Phillips *et al.*, 2017). Semi-immunity, characterized by the host's ability to tolerate and - to an extent - suppress blood stage infection, is acquired over the course of several disease episodes (Gonzales *et al.*, 2020; Nahrendorf *et al.*, 2019). This semi-

immunity is most often attributed to antibody-mediated control of parasitemia (resistance) (Gonzales *et al.*, 2020) and to an ability to tone down overarching inflammatory responses during peak infection (tolerance) (Nahrendorf *et al.*, 2019). Importantly, even numerous blood stage infections do not induce sterile immunity and people living in endemic areas are repeatedly infected throughout their lives.

This fact has led to the notion that blood stage infection induces a form of unnatural and ineffective immunity. In individuals who have shown resistance to malaria, haemoglobin genotype has also been implicated (Goncalves *et al.*, 2017). There is a growing epidemiological and molecular evidence that report a relationship between haemoglobin genotype and the relative risk of infection with *Plasmodium falciparum* (Amala and Nwibani, 2015; Sani, 2014).

Haemoglobin (Hb) is the protein present in red blood cells that transport oxygen to the body's tissues and organs and give blood its red colour (Britannica, 2020). Types of haemoglobin (Hb) genotype have been found to be crucial to the rate of red blood cell parasite invasion, multiplication, and destruction as well as outcome of malaria disease (Nwaneri and Ibadin, 2011). The intracellular protein found in erythrocytes called haemoglobin is made up of four polypeptide globin chains that are folded around heme molecules. It is in charge of moving carbon dioxide from the tissues to the lungs and oxygen from the lungs to the tissues.

The globin chains are known to have many alleles and are encoded by the relevant genes on chromosomes 11 and 16. Many of these genotypes experience single amino acid alterations in the globin moiety as a consequence of point mutations in the DNA sequence. This results in the synthesis of different types of haemoglobins (Weatherall, 2011). An essential blood component that predicts haemoglobinopathies is haemoglobin (Hb) genotype (Esan *et al.*, 2012). The pigment of red blood cells that carries oxygen is called haemoglobin; genetic flaws can result in defective haemoglobin, which causes a disorder known as haemoglobinopathies (Safko, 2008).

There is one normal haemoglobin (Hb-AA) and five variants: Hb-AS, Hb-SS, Hb-SC, Hb-AC, and Hb-CC (Britannica, 2020). The inheritance of Hb-S from both parents results in a homozygous state (Hb-SS) known as sickle cell anaemia/disease (SCA/SCD). In contrast, the inheritance of Hb-S from one parent and Hb-A from the other leads to a heterozygous state (Hb-AS) which is known as sickle cell trait (SCT) (CDC, 2022).

Normal haemoglobin (Hb AA) and other abnormal haemoglobins, such as the mutant haemoglobin S (Hb S), are both part of haemoglobin genotypes. Abnormal haemoglobin genotype (Hb S) differ from normal genotype (Hb A) in that the neutral amino acid valine is substituted for glutamic acid at position 6 in the β -chain, which changes the characteristics of haemoglobin and causes red blood cells to sickle (Jeremiah, 2006).

The relationship between Hb genotype and level of protection conferred against severe forms of malaria remains unclear. Studies have also revealed that the haemoglobin variants also influence the distribution and transmission of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria in humans (Goncalves *et al.*, 2017). Two haemoglobinopathies-HbS and HbC (with genotypes AS and AC respectively) have been reported to protect against severe malaria compared with their HbAA counterparts but the influence of these two haemoglobinopathies on other parameters that are not directly linked to malaria severity varies. Different hypotheses have been proposed to explain the protection

conferred by haemoglobin genotypes AS and AC against malaria. They include, but not limited to, impaired development of the parasite at the blood stage, reduced cytoadherence of infected RBCs and enhanced acquisition of immunity (Cholera *et al.*, 2008; Goncalves *et al.*, 2017; LaMonte *et al.*, 2012).

Furthermore, protein targets of specific antibodies may be more exposed on the surface of RBCs with Hb S or C resulting in enhanced immunity. However, concerning other parameters such as gametocyte carriage and infection chronicity, they differ. HbS has been associated with reduced gametocyte carriage while HbC has been associated with frequent gametocyte carriage (Goncalves *et al.*, 2017; Williams, 2011). Due to the nature of the malaria burden in Nigeria and with 97% of the population being at risk of infection (Dawaki *et al.*, 2016), quite a few studies have been carried out to evaluate the role that haemoglobin genotypes play on the distribution of *P. falciparum* malaria among the populace. This study therefore was designed to evaluate the distribution/relationship of haemoglobin genotypes among malaria-positive individuals in Nasarawa State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **Study design**

The study sites were **Akwanga, Keffi and Lafia** which represent the three senatorial districts of Nasarawa State. Nasarawa State with 13 local government areas is one of the 36 states in Nigeria and is situated in the North-Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria, bordering the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) to the north, Kaduna State to the northwest, Plateau State to the northeast, Taraba State to the east, and Benue State to the South. The state capital is Lafia, which is also the largest city. The state has an area of 26256km² and a population of about 1,826883 at the 2006 census (Wikipedia, 2015), though is currently projected to be about 2,886,000 (Projection, 2022).

Figure 1: Map of Nasarawa State showing study area (source: Google screenshot)

- **Ethical approval and consent**

Ethical approval was obtained from the Nasarawa State Health Research Ethics Committee (NHREC Protocol No: 18/06/2017) while oral consent was obtained from the subjects who offered to participate in the study upon meeting the criteria for the selection.

- **Sample Size**

The sample size was calculated with a 95% Confidence Interval (CI) and precision level of 5% using the standard sample size calculation formula described by Naing *et al.*, (2006).

$$n = Z^2P(1 - P)/d^2$$

Where:

n = Sample size if the target population is > 10,000

Z = Z statistic for a level of confidence (For 95% confidence level, Z = 1.96)

P = Expected prevalence or proportion (in proportion of one; if 50%, P = 0.5) and

d = Precision (in proportion of one; if 5%, d = 0.05).

Given that Z = 1.96, P = 0.5, d = 0.05 and substituting the values, sample size was calculated thus:

$$n = 1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.5 (1 - 0.5) \div 0.05 \times 0.05$$

$$n = 3.8416 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 \div 0.0025$$

$$n = 0.9604 \div 0.0025$$

$$n = 384.16$$

Approximately, 384 positive samples were collected and used for the study.

A total of 384 malaria patients confirmed with *Plasmodium falciparum* after diagnoses in hospitals who volunteered to participate were included in this study.

- **Sample Collection and analysis**

Blood sample was collected by Medical Laboratory Scientist using venipuncture technique. The arm of the patient was tied with a tourniquet and the position of the veins was disinfected using a swab soaked in methylated spirit. Blood was collected into ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) tube and was transported to the hematology unit of the laboratory for analysis.

- **Malaria parasite detection and count**

Thick and thin blood film smear were made to determine the parasite density as described by WHO criteria for malaria parasite density (WHO, 2000; Cheesebrough, 2005). Thin film was made to identify the species of the malaria parasite (Cheesebrough, 2005).

Changes in parasitized red blood cells help to identify *plasmodium* species and to detect mixed infection of malaria parasite. The number of asexual *P. falciparum* and other species per 100 leukocytes were counted and if ten or more parasites were identified, then the number was recorded, a blood sample was regarded as negative if the examination of thick films failed to show the presence of asexual parasites. The parasite count in relation to the leukocyte count was converted to parasite per micro liter of blood (assuming 6000 leukocytes per micro liter of blood) using the formula below:

$$\text{Parasites}/\mu\text{of blood} = \frac{\text{No. of parasites counted} \times 6000}{\text{No. of leukocyte counted}}$$

- **Determination of haemoglobin (Hb) genotype**

The buffer (Tris-acetate-borate buffer) was poured into the electrophoresis chamber. Cellulose acetate paper was cut in 40mm by 60mm rectangular size and placed inside the electrophoresis

tank, with the shiny side down to soak in the buffer solution for 20 minutes. The buffer-soaked cellulose acetate paper was brought out using a stainless blunt tip forceps and placed between two layers of blotting papers to extract excess buffer from it but not to wipe dry. Using an applicator stick, 0.5ml of the already prepared hemolysate samples and already known heterozygous hemoglobin genotype AS control were applied on the cellulose acetate paper. The loaded acetate paper was immediately placed in the electrophoresis tank using the forceps. The tank was connected to the power supply and switched on to allow current run for 15 – 20 minutes. The result of hemoglobin variant distribution was read and recorded immediately. The control was used to match the different hemoglobin variants according to their migration on the cellulose acetate paper as electric current was passed through it (Khon,1969). The results were graded into HbAA, HbAS, HbSS and HbAC.

- **Statistical Analysis**

All data were inputted into Microsoft Excel then exported to SPSS version 21.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA) for descriptive analysis. Pearson's chi-square test was used to determine the association between, haemoglobin genotypes, demographic factors and the malaria parasite. Graphs were represented using descriptive bar charts to display association where necessary. P values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant at a confidence interval of 95%.

RESULTS

- **Distribution of Malaria in relation to gender**

A total number of 384 individuals infected with malaria were considered for this study. Of the infected individuals, 230(59.9%) and 154(40.1%) were females and males respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Gender distribution in the sampled malaria population

- **Distribution of Malaria in relation to age**

The distribution of the age group recorded 39(10.2%) subjects for the age group 10-20 years, 148(38.5%) 21-30 years, 105(27.3%) 31- 40 years, 44(11.5%) 41-50 years, 37(9.6%) 51-60 years and 11(2.9%) 60-70 years respectively (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Age distribution in the malaria population

- **Distribution of Haemoglobin (Hb) genotypes in the sampled population**

The distribution of haemoglobin genotypes in the sampled malaria populations are 307(79.9%) AA 74(19.3%) AS, 2(0.5%) SS and 1(0.3%) AC, as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Distribution of major genotypes in the population

- **Distribution of Haemoglobin (Hb) genotypes against gender status of malaria susceptible individuals**

The distribution of genotypes in females were 190(82.6%) AA, 39(17.0%) AS and 1(0.4%) SS while males are 117(76.0%) AA, 35(22.7%) AS, 1(0.6%) SS and 1(0.6%) AC (Figure 5). A Pearson chi-square value of 3.677 and a non-significant p-value of 0.299 were obtained.

Figure 5: Gender distribution of genotypes in the malaria population

- **Distribution of genotypes against age range of the malaria individuals.**

Of the 384 malaria individuals in the sampled population; the age ranges in the individual genotypes are 34(87.2%) AA, 5(12.8%) AS between 10-20 years, 113(76.4%) AA, 33(22.3%) AS, 1(0.7%) AC and 1(0.7%) SS between 21-30 years, 85(81.0%)AA and 20(19.0) AS between 31-40 years, 38(86.4%) AA, 5(11.4%) AS and 1(2.3%) SS between 41-50 years, 29(78.4%) AA and 8(21.6%) AS between 51-60 years, 8(72.7%) AA and 3(27.3%) AS between 61-70years (Figure 6). A Pearson chi-square value of 9.520 and a non-significant p-value of 0.849 were obtained.

Figure 6: Age distribution of genotypes in the sampled population

DISCUSSION

Malaria is a complicated illness that is influenced by numerous unclear host genetic variables (Amodu *et al.*, 2019; Egan, 2018; Driss *et al.*, 2011; Band *et al.*, 2022). The hemoglobin variants like hemoglobin S (HbS), hemoglobin C (HbC), and -thalassemia have been implicated in malaria infestation. Some studies have suggested that some monogenic human diseases confer remarkable levels of protection against severe, life-threatening *falciparum* malaria in African children, with a reducing risk of about 70% in homozygosity HbC and 90% in heterozygosity HbS individuals (Band *et al.*, 2022; Hedrick, 2011; Hemming *et al.*, 2022; Kariuki and Williams, 2020). However, within malaria-endemic areas, hemoglobin S (HbS) has developed into a persistent polymorphism that is linked to a shorter life expectancy in homozygous sickle cell disease sufferers and a longer life expectancy in heterozygous people who are less likely to suffer from malaria (Bougouma *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, Africa population have high frequencies of HbS along with other erythrocyte variants that offer defense against the severe illnesses of *P. falciparum* infection, while *P. falciparum* have advanced a vast repertoire of genetic mutations to elude the human immune system and resist antimalarial medications (Band *et al.*, 2022; Hedrick, 2011; Hemming *et al.*, 2022; Kariuki and Williams, 2020).

There is an evolving knowledge on the relationship between different hemoglobin variants and malaria parasites (Band *et al.*, 2022). To expand the transforming focus on eliminating malaria, it is pertinent to understand how common genotypic variants such as AA, AS and SS affect malaria parasite. Here we access the relationship between major haemoglobin variants and the laboratory outcomes of patients with malaria in the Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

In the study, out of the 384 patients confirmed with malaria, the frequency distribution of AA (79.9%) and AS (19.3%) in this study agrees with the AA(78.95%) and AS(13.68%) recorded by Onohuean *et al.*,(2023) in South West Uganda though with smaller sample size of 155. The 73.20% of AA and 19.9% of AS reported by Cheesbrough (2005) at Burkina Faso is also similar to our findings. A study conducted in Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria by Njila *et al.*, (2022) recorded 70% AA and 9% SS genotypes. Though, our results are similar to the aforementioned reported outcomes, there were however in contrast with the results of Gboeloh *et al.*, (2022) who reported 62.1% AA and 33% AS conducted at Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Rivers State and Griffin *et al.*, (2015) who also recorded 64.2% AA and 30.9% AS. It is possible that the high prevalence of AA genotype in this study may be attributed to natural selection against SS genotype (Bougouma *et al.*, 2012).

It is also an indication that AA genotype is highly susceptible to malaria (Archer, 2018; Komba *et al.*, 2009; Njila *et al.*, 2022; Williams *et al.*, 2005). Our study accounted for a significantly increased frequency of malaria parasitaemia to be distributed more in individuals with the AA genotype when compared to the other haemoglobin genotypes. The decreased distribution of HbAS and HbSS genotypes in our finding implies that individuals with HbAS and HbSS gene enjoyed protection against malaria provided by the presence of haemoglobin S.

The malaria parasites thrive better in an oxygen-enriched environment provided by the haemoglobin genotype AA, unlike what occurs with abnormal haemoglobin genotype HbSS which is not oxygen-rich, polymerized and poorly digested by the parasite, resulting in the accumulation of haemin which inhibits the replication and survival of the parasites (Abkarian *et al.*, 2011; Ito *et al.*, 2018; Opara *et al.*, 2016;). In normal haemoglobin A (HbA), the parasite enzyme known as malarial haem polymerase converts the harmful component of hemoglobin known as haemin (ferriprotoporphyrin) into the non-toxic chemical known as haemozoin during digestion, allowing the parasite to survive. However, because the parasite has difficulty digesting HbS, haemin builds up and prevents the parasite from reproducing and surviving in red blood cells that contain HbS (Ito *et al.*, 2018).

The percentage of haemoglobin genotype AS in our study (19.3%) is higher than the earlier reported figure of 13.68% by Onohuean *et al.*, (2023) but lower than 23.8% reported by Onaiwu *et al.*, (2019); 30.9% by Gboeloh *et al.*, (2022). The results obtained in our study and publications from previous and similar studies show that malaria infection rates tend to be low in HbSS followed by HbAS. These differences could have been attributed to sample size used by the authors. The consistency of our reports with earlier studies is an indication that the allele that causes sickle cell anaemia, HbS offers resistance to the malaria infection. This is because the HbS is well known to interfere with the growth and reproduction of the malaria parasites, which is possible through the reduction in the intake of oxygen due to the sickle nature of red cell, that

results in the removal of sickle red cells from circulation before the malaria parasites are able to complete their life cycle (Amala and Nwibani, 2015; Ebadan *et al.*, 2017; Akhigbe *et al.*, 2009).

The low malaria prevalence (0.5%) observed in haemoglobin genotype SS is in agreement with the findings of other scholars (Awotua-Efebo *et al.*, 2004; Khera, 2017; Kotila *et al.*, 2007; Komba *et al.*, 2009; Fada *et al.*, 2020; Purohit *et al.*, 2018). The low level of parasitemia recorded in this study and several other studies is believed to be as a result of the protective effect of the mutant gene (HbS) causing accelerated clearance of the malaria parasites and the hypoxia in red blood cells (Fada *et al.*, 2020). It could also be as a result of the awareness created during marriage counseling in recent times. Malaria parasitemia between females and males in patients with haemoglobin genotype AA was not statistically significant, although females (59.9%) were numerically infected than males (40.1%). Other scholars (Cholera *et al.*, 2008; Tossea *et al.*, 2018; Sangare, 2019) also recorded greater frequency of females than males. The higher prevalence of malaria among females in our study could be attributed to differences in exposure patterns, or clothing that increase susceptibility to mosquito bites. In addition, the hormonal fluctuations in females could potentially explain the gender-based differences in malaria susceptibility.

CONCLUSION

This study provides evidence that haemoglobin genotypes play a critical role in malaria susceptibility in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The AA genotype was more susceptible to malaria, while AS and SS genotypes offer some level of protection against the disease. These findings are consistent with previous studies and highlight the importance of considering haemoglobin variants in malaria prevention and treatment strategies. This study calls for a multi-state studies with larger sample sizes, which would enable researchers and analysts to capture a more diverse population and account for regional variations in malaria transmission and genetics. Additionally, it is important to note that other biological markers might play crucial roles in malaria susceptibility and should therefore be assessed.

- **Limitation of the study**

While our study provides key insights into the relationship between haemoglobin genotypes and malaria susceptibility, there are potential limitations to consider. For instance, our sample size was limited to 384 malaria-positive individuals, which might have impacted our ability to detect significant differences between groups. The lack of a control group in our study hampers our ability to compare haemoglobin genotypes distributions between malaria patients and healthy individuals. Additionally, the cross-sectional design precluded inference of causality between haemoglobin genotypes and malaria susceptibility, the hospital-based sample could have possibly introduced selection bias, as individuals seeking medical care may not be representative of the general population. Furthermore, unmeasured variables such as socioeconomic factors, immunity and access to healthcare may have influenced the findings in our study.

- **Recommendations:**

Based on the findings of this study, the authors recommend the following:

1. Haemoglobin genotype screening should be included in malaria prevention and treatment programs to identify individuals at high risk of infection.
2. Targeted interventions should be implemented to protect individuals with the AA genotype, who are more susceptible to malaria.
3. Future studies should aim to investigate the mechanisms underlying the protective effect of AS and SS genotypes against malaria.
4. Future studies replicating this study should include control groups for both malaria patients and healthy individuals.

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- **Conflict of Interest**

The authors declare that they have no financial commitments or other relationships that might lead to any conflict.

REFERENCES:

- Adel Driss, Jacqueline M Hibbert , Nana O Wilson , Shareen A Iqbal , Thomas V Adamkiewicz and Jonathan K Stiles (2011). Genetic polymorphisms linked to susceptibility to malaria. *Malaria Journal* 10:271 <http://www.malariajournal.com/content/10/1/271>.
- Akhigbe, R. E., Ige, S. F., Adegunlola, G. J., Adewumi, M. O., & Azeez, M. O. (2011). Malaria, haemoglobin genotypes and ABO blood groups in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *International Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 6, 73–76.
- Akhigbe, R. E., Ige, S. F., Afolabi, A. O., Azeez, O. M., Adegulola, G. L., & Bamidele, J. O. (2009). Prevalence of haemoglobin variant, ABO and Rhesus blood group in Lodeke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho, Nigeria. *Trends in Medical Research*, 4, 24–29.
- Amala, S. E., & Nwibani, C. P. (2015). Malaria in pregnancy and its association with ABO blood group and haemoglobin genotype.
- Archer, N. M., Peterson, N., Clark, M. A., Buckee, C. O., Childs, L. M., & Duraisingh, M. T. (2018). Resistance to *Plasmodium falciparum* in sickle cell trait erythrocytes is driven by oxygen-dependent growth inhibition. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(28), 7350–7355.
- Bougouma, E. C., Tiono, A. B., Ouédraogo, A., Soulama, I., Diarra, A., Yaro, J. B., Ouédraogo, E., Sanon, S., Konaté, A. T., Nébié, I., Watson, N. L., Sanza, M., Dube, T. J., & Sirima, S. B. (2012). Haemoglobin variants and *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria in children

- under five years of age living in a high and seasonal malaria transmission area of Burkina Faso. *Malaria Journal*, 11, 154.
- Britannica (2020). The Editors of Encyclopaedia. hemoglobin. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. [Accessed 2022 Mar 08]. Available from: <https://www.britannica.com/science/hemoglobin>.
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention. (2022). *Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)*.
- Cheesbrough, M. (2005). Examination of blood for parasites. In *District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Cheesbrough, M. (2022). Examination of blood for parasites. In *District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Cholera, R., Brittain, N. J., Gillrie, M. R., Lopera-Mesa, T. M., Diakite, S. A., Arie, T., Krause, M. A., Guindo, A., Tubman, A., Fujioka, H., Diallo, D. A., Doumbo, O. K., Ho, M., Wellems, T. E., & Fairhurst, R. M. (2008). Impaired cytoadherence of *Plasmodium falciparum*-infected erythrocytes containing sickle hemoglobin. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 105(3), 991–996. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0711401105.
- Cowman AF, Healer J, Marapana D, Marsh K (2016). *Malaria: Biology and Disease*. Cell [Internet].;167(3):61024. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S009286741631008X>.
- Driss, A.; Hibbert, J.M.; Wilson, N.O.; Iqbal, S.A.; Adamkiewicz, T.V.; Stiles, J.K. (2015) Genetic polymorphisms linked to susceptibility to malaria. *Malar. J.*, 10, 271. [CrossRef] [PubMed].
- Ebadan, M. I., Obodo, B. N., Amiegheme, F. E., Uwaifo, F., Omigie, B. E., Iyevhobu, L. K., Umassor, A. C., & Aiyeki, G. E. (2017). Prevalence and susceptibility of malaria parasites infection in association with blood group and hemoglobin genotype polymorphisms in pregnancy. *International Journal of Community Research*, 6(2), 2–8.
- Egan, J. E., S. L. Hoffman, J. D. Haynes, J. C. Sadoff, I. Schneider, G. E. Grau, M. R. Hollingdale, W. R. Ballou, and D. M. Gordon (2018). Humoral immune response in volunteers immunized with irradiated *Plasmodium falciparum* sporozoites. *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 49:166–173.
- Esan, A. (2015). Assessment of haemoglobin variants in malaria infected individuals using haematological parameters. *International Journal of Hematological Disorders*, 2(1), 4-9. doi: 10.12691/ijhd-2-1-2.
- Gavin Band, Ellen M. Leffler, Muminatou Jallow, Fatoumatta Sisay-Joof, Carlyne M. Ndila, Alexander W. Macharia, Christina Hubbart, Anna E. Jeffreys, Kate Rowlands, Thuy Nguyen, Sónia Gonçalves, Cristina V. Ariani, Jim Stalker, Richard D. Pearson, Roberto Amato, Eleanor Drury, Giorgio Sirugo, Umberto d’Alessandro, Kalifa A. Bojang, Kevin

- Marsh, Norbert Peshu, Joseph W. Saelens, Mahamadou Diakit, Steve M. Taylor, David J. Conway, Thomas N. Williams, Kirk A. Rockett & Dominic P. Kwiatkowski. (2022). Malaria protection due to sickle haemoglobin depends on parasite genotype. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-04288-3>.
- Gboeloh, L. B., Wordu, E., & Josiah, A. E. (2022). Relationship between malaria parasitemia and haemoglobin variants in patients attending Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. *Open Access Research Journal of Life Sciences*, 4(1), 16–26.
- Goncalves, B. P., Sagara, I., Coulibaly, M., Wu, Y., Assadou, M. H., Guindo, A., Ellis, R. D., Diakite, M., Gabriel, E., Prevots, D. R., Doumbo, O. K., & Duffy, P. E. (2017). Hemoglobin variants shape the distribution of malaria parasites in human populations and their transmission potential. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1), 14267. doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-14627-y
- Griffin, J. T., Hollingsworth, T. D., Reyburn, H., Drakeley, C. J., Riley, E. M., & Ghani, A. C. (2015). Gradual acquisition of immunity to severe malaria with increasing exposure. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 282(1801), 20142657.
- Ito, E., Egwunyenga, A., & Ake, J. (2014). Prevalence of malaria and human blood factors among patients in Ethiop East, Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Medicine and Biomedical Research*, 3(3), 191-201.
- Jeremiah ZA, Jeremiah TA, Emelike FO: Frequencies of some human genetic markers and their association with Plasmodium falciparum malaria in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *J Vector Borne Dis* 2010, 47:11–16.
- Jeremiah, Z. A. (2006). Abnormal hemoglobin variants, ABO, and Rh blood groups among students of African descent in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *African Health Sciences*, 6(3), 177-181. doi: 10.5555/afhs.2006.6.3.177.
- Kariuki SN, Williams TN (2020). Human genetics and malaria resistance. *Hum Genet* ;139:801–11.
- Komba, A. N., Makani, J., Sadarangani, M., Abgo, T. A., Berkely, J. A., Newton, C. R. J. C., Marsh, K., & Williams, T. N. (2009). Malaria as a cause of morbidity and mortality in children with homozygous sickle cell disease on the coast of Kenya. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 49(2), 216-222.
- LaMonte, G., Philip, N., Reardon, J., Lacsina, J. R., Majoros, W., Chapman, L., Thornburg, C. D., Telen, M. J., Ohler, U., Nicchitta, C. V., Haystead, T., & Chi, J. T. (2012). Translocation of sickle cell erythrocyte microRNAs into Plasmodium falciparum inhibits parasite translation and contributes to malaria resistance. *Cell Host & Microbe*, 12(2), 187-199. doi: 10.1016/j.chom.2012.06.007

- Nwaneri DU, Ibadin MO. (2011). Haemoglobin genotype of children with severe malaria seen at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Benin city, Nigeria. DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/njp.v39i2.2>.
- Sani, M. (2014). The study of ABO blood groups and haemoglobin genotypes in Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research Studies in Biosciences*, 12(1), 198-200.
- Weatherall DJ, Clegg JB (2002). Genetic variability in response to infection: malaria and after. *Genes Immun*, 3:331-337.
- William T, Jelip J, Menon J, Anderios F, Mohammad R, Awang Mohammad TA, (2014). Changing epidemiology of malaria in Sabah, Malaysia: increasing incidence of *Plasmodium knowlesi*. *Malar J.*;13:390.
- Williams TN (2011). How do hemoglobins S and C result in malaria protection? *J Infect Dis*, 204:1651–1653.
- Williams TN, Mwangi TW, Roberts DJ, Alexander ND, Weatherall DJ, Wambua S, Kortok M, Snow RW, Marsh K. (2005). An immune basis for malaria protection by the sickle cell trait. *PLoS Med*, 2:e128.
- Williams TN, Mwangi TW, Wambua S, Alexander ND, Kortok M, Snow RW, Marsh K (2005). Sickle cell trait and the risk of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria and other childhood diseases. *J Infect Dis*, 192:178–186.
- Williams TN, Obaro SK (2011). Sickle cell disease and malaria morbidity: a tale with two tails. *Trends Parasitol*, 27:315–320.
- Williams TN, Obaro SK: Sickle cell disease and malaria morbidity: a tale with two tails. *Trends Parasitol* 2011, 27:315–320.
- Williams TN: How do hemoglobins S and C result in malaria protection? *J Infect Dis* 2011, 204:1651–1653.
- Williams, T. N. (2011). How do hemoglobins S and C result in malaria protection? *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 204(11), 1651-1653. (link unavailable)
- World Health Organization. (2022). *World Malaria Report 2022*.
- World Health Organization. (2023). *World Malaria Report 2023*.
- World Health Organization. (2024). *World Malaria Report 2024*.